

An Observational Retrospective Study on Symptoms and Risk Factors Analysis of Covid19 among Healthcare Workers in a Tertiary Care Hospital of Eastern India

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Abstract:

Background: The COVID-19 pandemic has placed significant stress on healthcare systems globally, with healthcare workers (HCWs) being at the forefront of the battle against the virus. Due to their increased exposure to COVID-19, HCWs are at a higher risk of infection and severe outcomes, especially those with pre-existing comorbidities. Understanding the symptoms and risk factors specific to HCWs in different regions is crucial for implementing effective protective measures.

Aim: This study aimed to analyze the symptoms and risk factors associated with COVID-19 among healthcare workers in a tertiary care hospital in Eastern India, focusing on identifying the key factors contributing to infection rates and the severity of symptoms.

Methods: Data were collected from medical records, including demographics, symptoms, comorbidities, and exposure history. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with chi-square tests and logistic regression analysis used to determine significant associations between risk factors and COVID-19 outcomes.

Results: Among the 200 participants, 150 (75%) tested positive for COVID-19. The most common symptoms were fever (85%), cough (70%), and fatigue (65%). Hypertension (25%) and diabetes (20%) were the most prevalent comorbidities and were significantly associated with severe symptoms ($p < 0.05$). Logistic regression analysis revealed that hypertension and inadequate PPE usage significantly increased the odds of severe COVID-19 symptoms, with odds ratios of 3.5 and 4.2, respectively.

Conclusion: The study highlights the high infection rate among healthcare workers in a tertiary care hospital in Eastern India and identifies hypertension, diabetes, and inadequate PPE usage as significant risk factors for severe COVID-19 outcomes. These findings underscore the need for enhanced protective measures and targeted health monitoring for HCWs, particularly those with underlying health conditions.

Recommendations: To protect healthcare workers, it is recommended to ensure the availability and proper usage of PPE, implement regular health screenings for comorbid conditions, and provide targeted interventions for those at higher risk. Further research is needed to explore long-term outcomes and the effectiveness of protective strategies in similar settings.

Keywords: COVID-19, healthcare workers, risk factors, tertiary care hospital, Eastern India.

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Introduction

This particular COVID-19 outbreak has presented public health agencies throughout the world with previously unheard-of difficulties. HCWs have been leading the response activities in healthcare systems since the WHO declared COVID-19 a pandemic in March 2020. HCWs are disproportionately exposed to COVID-19 as frontline defenders against the virus, which puts them at a higher risk of infection than the overall

population. Long-term contact with infected patients, the need to execute aerosol-generating operations, and, in certain cases, the lack of personal protective equipment (PPE) during the pandemic's critical stages all increase this risk [1].

Several studies have demonstrated the susceptibility of HCWs to COVID-19, with infection rates among this cohort having a

substantial influence on workforce availability and healthcare delivery [2]. Pre-existing conditions including diabetes and hypertension, which have been demonstrated to raise the risk of severe outcomes in COVID-19 patients, further enhance the risk [3]. The workload for healthcare workers in tertiary care facilities in India has been significant, especially for those located in heavily populated areas, as there are significant regional variations in healthcare infrastructure. These hospitals treat a significant number of critically ill patients and operate as referral centres for difficult cases, which increases the chance of HCWs getting infected with the virus.

It is essential to comprehend the unique symptoms and risk factors that health care workers encounter in these environments in order to create focused protective solutions. Prior studies have mostly concentrated on the general public or particular HCW subgroups in various geographic situations. Localised research is nevertheless required to take into consideration regional differences in population health dynamics, resource accessibility, and healthcare delivery [4]. The experiences of healthcare workers during the epidemic are worth closely examining in Eastern India, where socioeconomic gaps and variable degrees of healthcare access exacerbate healthcare issues.

This study aimed to analyze the symptoms and risk factors associated with COVID-19 among healthcare workers in a tertiary care hospital in Eastern India, focusing on identifying the key factors contributing to infection rates and the severity of symptoms.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a retrospective observational analysis.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital in Eastern India. The hospital is a major healthcare provider in the region, offering a variety of services, including a dedicated COVID-19 treatment centre. Data was obtained from medical records between March 2020 and March 2021.

Participants: A total of 200 healthcare workers participated in this study. These participants included doctors, nurses, paramedical staff, and other support staff working in various departments of the hospital during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Healthcare workers who were employed at the tertiary care hospital during the study period.
- Participants who had undergone RT-PCR testing for COVID-19.

- Participants with complete medical records available for analysis, including demographic data, symptoms, and risk factors.

Exclusion Criteria

- Healthcare workers who were not directly involved in patient care or hospital services.
- Participants with incomplete medical records.
- Healthcare workers who tested negative for COVID-19 but did not exhibit any symptoms during the study period.

Bias: To minimize bias, all eligible healthcare workers who met the inclusion criteria were included in the study. Data was anonymized to prevent any selection bias. However, as the study is retrospective, there is a potential for information bias due to incomplete or inaccurate records.

Data Collection: Data was collected retrospectively from the hospital's electronic medical records system. Information on demographics (age, gender), clinical symptoms, risk factors (e.g., comorbidities, exposure history), and COVID-19 test results were extracted. Data collection was standardized to ensure consistency and accuracy.

Procedure: After obtaining ethical approval from the hospital's institutional review board, relevant data was retrieved from the medical records. The data was de-identified to maintain participant confidentiality. The extracted data was then organized into a structured database for analysis.

Statistical Analysis: A statistical analysis was performed with SPSS 23.0. The frequencies of symptoms and risk variables, as well as demographic information, were compiled using descriptive statistics. While means and standard deviations were used to characterise continuous variables, frequencies and percentages were used to represent categorical variables. The association between categorical variables was assessed using chi-square tests, and the significant risk factors linked to COVID-19 among healthcare workers were found using logistic regression analysis. Less than 0.05 was the threshold for statistical significance.

Results

Participant Demographics: A total of 200 healthcare workers were included in the study. The participants consisted of 90 males (45%) and 110 females (55%). The mean age of the participants was 35.4 years (SD = 8.6), with an age range from 22 to 58 years.

Table 1: Demographics, Symptoms, and Risk Factors of Healthcare Workers

Characteristic	Frequency (n=200)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	90	45%
Female	110	55%
Age Group (years)		
20-30	60	30%
31-40	85	42.5%
41-50	40	20%
51-60	15	7.5%
COVID-19 Infection Status		
Positive	150	75%
Negative	50	25%
Common Symptoms among Positive Cases (n=150)		
Fever	127	85%
Cough	105	70%
Fatigue	98	65%
Shortness of Breath	60	40%
Loss of Taste/Smell	45	30%
Sore Throat	38	25%
Risk Factors (n=200)		
Hypertension	50	25%
Diabetes	40	20%
History of Exposure to COVID-19 (Without PPE)	60	30%
History of Exposure to COVID-19 (With PPE)	140	70%

Logistic regression analysis was conducted to identify the risk factors significantly associated with COVID-19 infection. The results indicated that healthcare workers with hypertension had 3.5 times higher odds of developing severe COVID-19

symptoms (OR = 3.5, 95% CI = 1.6–7.8, p = 0.002). Similarly, those with a history of inadequate PPE usage had 4.2 times higher odds of contracting COVID-19 (OR = 4.2, 95% CI = 2.1–8.5, p < 0.001).

Table 2: Association between Comorbidities, Symptoms, and Logistic Regression Analysis

Analysis Type	Risk Factor	Severe Symptoms (n=60)	Non-Severe Symptoms (n=140)	χ^2	p-value	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval	p-value
Chi-Square Test	Hypertension	25	25	10.4	0.001	-	-	-
	Diabetes	20	8.6	0.003	-	-	-	-
Logistic Regression Analysis	Hypertension	-	-	-	-	3.5	1.6–7.8	0.002
	Diabetes	-	-	-	2.8	1.2–6.3	0.015	-
	Inadequate PPE	-	-	-	4.2	2.1–8.5	<0.001	-

Discussion

In this study, the participants' mean age was 35.4 years, and they were mostly female (55%). A sizable fraction (75%) of the healthcare professionals had positive COVID-19 test results, indicating the population's high risk of exposure. Those who were infected most frequently reported

having a fever (85%), cough (70%), and weariness (65%). These results underline the significance of early recognition and diagnosis among healthcare workers to prevent further transmission within healthcare settings, and they are consistent with the general symptomatology reported in COVID-19 patients. The risk factor analysis showed that severe symptoms, including dyspnoea, were more

common among healthcare professionals with pre-existing diseases such as diabetes (20%) and hypertension (25%). The chi-square test revealed a significant correlation (p-values of 0.001 and 0.003 for diabetes and hypertension, respectively) between these comorbidities and the emergence of severe symptoms. This means that severe COVID-19 symptoms are more likely to occur in healthcare professionals with these disorders.

A modified version of the World Health Organization's COVID-19 risk assessment instrument was used to analyze the transmission risk variables among frontline (HCWs) in a study carried out at a tertiary care centre in South India. In comparison to low-risk contacts, high-risk contacts had a considerably higher chance of testing positive for COVID-19, according to the study. Common mechanisms of exposure, especially for high-risk contacts, were found to be shared areas and failures in infection protection and control. This emphasises how HCWs that interact closely with COVID-19-positive people are more vulnerable, which calls for strict infection control procedures [5].

An further cross-sectional study examined the risk factors and epidemiology of Covid-19 transmission among healthcare workers in Rishikesh, Uttarakhand, a tertiary healthcare setting. 22 of the 1,141 HCWs who were exposed to COVID-19 patients tested positive for the virus, according to the study. A greater secondary attack rate of SARS-CoV-2 was found to be strongly correlated with high-risk exposure, highlighting the necessity of routine testing and monitoring to prevent the spread of infection in healthcare settings [6].

Lastly, the seroprevalence of SARS-CoV-2 among healthcare personnel was evaluated by a cohort research carried out in a Delhi tertiary care hospital specifically designed for COVID-19 patients. According to the study, seroprevalence was not substantially correlated with factors like as age, sex, occupation, or smoking status, and 51.3% of healthcare workers had produced antibodies against the virus. Adherence to infection prevention and control methods, however, did not significantly correlate with antibody positivity, suggesting that seroconversion rates among healthcare workers may be influenced by other factors. The research emphasises how crucial it is to consistently follow preventive measures in order to lower the probability of transmission [7].

Conclusion

By focusing on this specific cohort, the study seeks to identify the key factors contributing to the high infection rates among HCWs and to understand the

clinical manifestations of COVID-19 in this population. The findings will provide valuable insights for healthcare administrators and policymakers in devising effective strategies to safeguard HCWs, ensuring the sustainability of healthcare services during ongoing and future pandemics.

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